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*David Fasenfest*¹

*Alfredo Saad-Filho*²

GLOBAL POVERTY: A MARXIAN ANALYSIS*

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Расширенная аннотация статьи на русском языке¹

Неоклассический мейнстрим утверждает, что бедность порождается социальной изоляцией и отделением от рыночных процессов, которые, в свою очередь, вызываются провалами рынка или спонтанными ограничениями добровольного обмена. С наступлением кейнсианства, социальной демократии и государств всеобщего благосостояния в развитых капиталистических экономиках были расширены гражданские права рабочего класса, институализиро-

валась динамика номинальных зарплат, расширились возможности рабочих в борьбе за большую долю дохода при росте производительности. Обеспечение населения базовыми товарами и услугами государством всеобщего благосостояния, финансируемое за счет прогрессивного налогообложения, было направлено на снижение неравенства, социальную интеграцию и политическую стабильность. Это включило цели социальной борьбы в господствующую парадигму, разоружив радикальных левых и революционную повестку из политических дебатов. Снижение бедности и экономический рост существовали одновременно. Это дало основание заявлениям, что рост напрямую снижает бедность. В результате были расшире-

¹ *Перевод расширенной аннотации с англ. яз.:* Маслов Глеб Андреевич, кандидат экономических наук, научный сотрудник Центра методологических и историко-экономических исследований Института экономики РАН.

¹ *David Fasenfest*, PhD, Department of Sociology, Wayne State University, Detroit, USA (*critical.sociology@gmail.com*).

² *Alfredo Saad-Filho*, PhD, Department of International Development, King's College London (*alfredo.saad-filho@kcl.ac.uk*).

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ны программы, нацеленные на приобретение социального компромисса для сдерживания политических протестов. Но что не рассматривается мейнстримом, так это идея того, что бедность может быть следствием глобального капиталистического производства, усиленным неолиберальной политикой.

К началу XXI века неолиберальная политика жесткой экономии вынудила правительства стать зависимыми от финансовых рынков для предоставления общественных услуг своим избирателям. Усилилась городская и сельская бедность, так как в условиях жесткой экономии органы власти не могли оказывать социальную поддержку. С точки зрения критического взгляда политической экономии, бедность унижает человеческое достоинство и означает утрату человеческого потенциала, что негативно сказывается как на отдельных людях, так и на обществе в целом.

Исследовательский взгляд Маркса отражает радикальные демократические и антикапиталистические социальные изменения, стремится им содействовать. Маркс предлагает более полное сравнительно с мейнстримной экономикой представление о бедности, неравенстве, их динамике. Его философские идеи, особенно его концентрация на материальных аспектах жизни, крайне актуальны, когда материальные потребности большинства остаются неудовлетворенными. Маркс обращается к вопросу как накопление капитала создает различные формы бедности. Бедность и неравенство имеют структурный и тенденциозный характер при капитализме, и их существование можно объяснить с политической точки зрения.

Капитализм регулярно повышает производительность труда, и рабочий класс потенциально может получать дополнительные материальные выгоды.

Однако их содержание и масштабы будут определяться коллективными действиями. Демократические цели и процессы по своей сути благоприятны, они больше соответствуют интересам подавляющего большинства населения, чем экономические стратегии, связанные с идеями мейнстрима и международным финансовым рынком.

Государственная политика должна играть ключевую роль в демократической экономической стратегии. Не только с точки зрения ресурсной мобилизации, международного влияния, силы закона, но и потому что государство – это фундаментальное средство коллективного действия. Чего не хватает для внедрения этой стратегии, так это недостаток достаточных политических возможностей для воплощения альтернативной политики, а также эффективного и вовлеченного рабочего движения. В настоящее время активность рабочего класса находится на самом низком уровне за два поколения, и он терпит самые большие поражения за несколько лет. Однако, что точно дает марксистский анализ, так это то, что конец капитализма может наступить только в результате социальной борьбы. Мы утверждаем, что без революционной составляющей борьбы, без революционной теории большинство людей так и будут оставаться угнетенным, а бедность сохранится.

Это фундаментальные условия демократии – не традиционно понимаемой неолиберальной демократии, а радикальной демократии в представлении Маркса, той, которая не может быть совместима с капитализмом. Есть бесчисленное количество примеров, когда люди, казалось бы, побеждали в своей борьбе с бедностью, но не смогли освободиться от капиталистических общественных отношений. Построение

настоящего альтернативного социализма – это задача, которой должны заняться все марксисты для освобождения людей как от капиталистического империализма, так и от потенциально искаженных форм социализма.

Introduction

The Reverend Thomas Malthus believed that the poor had an awful tendency to multiply faster than the means of subsistence. In this case, charity or public programmes to alleviate poverty may be well-intentioned, but they would create even more misery down the line, as the poor suffered the consequences of their own growing numbers. Underpinning Malthus's pessimism is the belief that poverty was, immediately, the outcome of misbehaviour to be corrected or even a crime to be suppressed but, ultimately, poverty (as well as wealth) was divinely ordained. Accordingly, the English workhouses in the 19th Century were meant to terrorise poor people into submission to capital under the guise of providing relief; the perfect solution for capital.

In an incomparably more sophisticated garb, but along similar lines, mainstream (orthodox or neoclassical) economics today argues that poverty is created by social exclusion (defined as segregation from market processes), which is caused by market failure or by the imposition of arbitrary constraints to voluntary exchange. In other words, as Jesus says in Matthew 26:11 (and Mark 14:7), 'The poor you will always have with you' – except in the very long term, when capitalist processes finally manage to lift the curse of absolute deprivation. From this point of view, then, poverty can be measured by the inability to achieve some arbitrary expenditure line, implying that money brings satisfaction, markets are the source

of wealth, and market integration is the main force for economic growth and the reduction of absolute poverty.

In the period after World War II, the rise of Keynesianism, social democracy and the welfare state in the advanced capitalist economies in the West resulted in an expanded set of citizenship rights of the working class, the institutionalisation of the downward rigidity of nominal wages, and the right of the workers to claim a share of the fruits of productivity growth. Public provision of basic goods and services through the welfare state, funded by progressive taxation, reduced inequality and promoted social integration and political stability. They incorporated most opposition into the hegemonic system, disarming the radical left and excluding revolutionary options from political debates and, increasingly, from admissibility in the political imaginary. In the developing countries, where policy debates were increasingly framed by the orthodox policies of stabilisation and structural adjustment led by the International Monetary Fund and the World Bank, the discourses of poverty reduction and growth blended together, through the assumption that growth directly reduces poverty, supplemented by minimalist, targeted and conditional social programmes aiming to buy social peace and contain political revolt.

What is not generally seriously considered in the mainstream literature is the idea that poverty could be a consequence of the spread of capitalist production globally, exacerbated by neoliberal policies. As is well known, neoclassical economics is constructed around notions of scarcity and profit and utility maximisation. This approach assumes that individuals have limited means, and they are by definition unable to satisfy all their (infinite) wants. What

follows is a presumably 'rational' war of all against all, tempered by law, and framed as competition mediated by self-interest. In other words, in capitalist economies everything is about profits and, consequently, accumulation and growth; similarly, neoclassical economics has only a secondary concern with the dynamics of productivity growth, structural change, and different ways to satisfy needs and wants: the focus remains firmly on a static equilibrium analysis focusing on the allocation of scarce resources among competing ends.

The background to the mainstream approach to growth, poverty and poverty alleviation is that the social preconditions for capitalism create poverty, both intentionally – through the generation of a dispossessed class of people – but also unintentionally, as millions are thrown into a human scrapheap from which they are unable to emerge. By the same token, following the commercial logic of capitalism, the dominant form of measurement of poverty remains monetary poverty lines, occasionally enriched by non-monetary indicators such as health, education, degrees of social exclusion and well-being measured through interviews with the poor, and so on.

From a critical political economy perspective, instead, poverty degrades human beings and represents a loss of human potential that affects negatively both individuals and society as a whole. At the levels of analysis and policy, in turn, poverty is a reflection of the failure of neoclassical economics to address and alleviate this scourge on the all-around development of human beings. Several decades of globalization, neoliberal policies and the imposition of 'fiscal austerity' in the service of the appropriation of the social surplus by a small segment of society reveals the long-term harm

that capitalism has done to humanity. We must turn to Marx in order both to evaluate the forces that create persistent poverty, and to examine how poverty and its consequences can be eliminated. This requires a two-pronged approach: changing the calculus of political economy in the industrialized North and recognizing that lessons from Marx can have an impact on how we deal with the Global South (see Fasenfest and Das, forthcoming).

We proceed in three stages: first we expand on the neoliberal turn in contemporary capitalism, which instituted a range of policies ultimately increasing poverty. Second, we explore why it is important to (re)turn to Marx to seek an understanding of and solution to global poverty. Finally, we pose some questions about the necessary political response in order to arrive at a transformation of the political, social and economic systems currently in place in a capitalist society.

The Neoliberal Turn

At the end of the Second World War, Western Europe was largely destroyed in terms of its productive capacities, and the United States was scrambling to convert war efforts back to peacetime production and to absorb millions of demobilized soldiers into the domestic labour force. Most Western governments turned to a Keynesian policy of securing full employment primarily through the regulation of (much higher levels of) spending by the government. Public investments to subsidize or build infrastructure like schools, hospitals, and highways (for example, the Federal Highway Act of 1956, under President Eisenhower, created the Interstate system of roads crisscrossing the country, and was one of the largest public works projects ever), investments to subsidize mass consumption through family allowances,

reducing indirect taxation, and keeping down the prices of necessities, or a combination of both initiatives (for example, low interest incentives to build affordable homes while giving households tax breaks for mortgage interest and real estate taxes paid), rapidly expanded the national economy. These programs were largely funded through higher levels of sharply progressive taxation, and growing fiscal deficits, which were financed by the proceeds of growth. Those government expenditures had the effect of increasing employment directly through funded projects, but also indirectly as rising incomes had multiplier effects on the general economy as consumer spending sustained increased employment on the part of small local businesses.

During the period between the 1950s and the 1970s, an increasingly tight labour market and government borrowing resulted in several systemic effects. Increased unionization and the need to retain workers during a period of expanding production drove up the wage bill and the share of wages in the national income. With expanded government borrowing to finance spending on programs, interest rates began to climb. Corporate profits were squeezed by a growing wage bill, rising social unrest since the mid-1960s, and a rising cost of capital. At the same time, the social solidarity that comes with greater unionization and society's awakening to material deprivation and multiple inequalities, including racial and gender inequality, as well as workplace health and safety, environmental degradation and eventually opposition to the war in Vietnam, led to periods of social unrest, mass demonstrations, and pressure on the US government to enact laws to address these issues. The climate for business was one of increasing regulation by an active

Congress, together with shrinking profits. The only way capital had to generate and sustain profits was to raise prices of goods and services, but in a low unemployment environment with strong unions this led to raising wages, which were offset again by more price increases, and so on, driving an inflationary spiral¹. It was not very different in Western Europe.

The political writing was on the wall as the business community sought political solutions to an increasingly unfriendly economic and social environment. To avoid a presumed 'collapse' of profits they turned to more business-friendly political campaigns, expecting elected officials to rein in organized labour, dismantle government regulations, and provide a friendlier tax environment. This resulted in the election of Ronald Reagan in 1980 in the US (Margaret Thatcher had been UK Prime Minister since 1979). Almost immediately government practices and policies changed. In 1981 the Professional Air Traffic Controllers Organization (PATCO) initiated what was called an 'illegal strike'² for better working conditions and wages. President Reagan dismissed the striking workers, broke the strike, and oversaw the decertification of the union. Shortly after, in 1984, the National Union of Mineworkers (NUM) struck in order to keep the coal mines open in the UK and protect jobs, that were being threatened by a massive programme of closures driven by the government. The National Coal Board, backed by Margaret Thatcher's Conservative government, opposed the strike and not only broke the trade union,

¹ By the end of 1979 the national inflation rate was 13.5 percent, the average 30-year mortgage rates reached 16.32 percent by April 1980, and corporations had to offer an average of 15.51 % interest on bonds issued to generate investment capital by October 1981.

² In a 1969 ruling by the U.S. Civil Service Commission, PATCO was deemed no longer to be a professional association but a trade union.

but essentially dismantled the industry and, with it, virtually eliminated the entire category of coal mining workers in Britain¹. Taken together, both actions by these business-friendly governments drastically reduced the power of the trade unions going forward.

A new era of so-called 'smaller government' and increasing deregulation created the foundation for a neoliberal agenda. Shifting from a largely nationally integrated economy, production in general and labour processes specifically were increasingly globalized. Financial regulations were relaxed to facilitate the mobility of capital and pave the way for financialization and eventually policies of 'austerity' to offset declining public revenues due to tax cuts. To further minimize the voices of workers and their communities, policy making increasingly shifted from government agencies and Congressional committees to closed circles of technocrats and privately funded think tanks. Looking at it retrospectively, the neoliberal state developed in ways that were unanticipated and, to some extent, chaotic (Harvey 2005: 64).

Where once the national government played an active role in managing social welfare, functions were devolved to states and local governments that were, in turn, hampered by their inability to generate the revenues necessary to fund essential public services². When the dust settled, a neoliberalism form of state and society

had become the new order of the day³, one which claims that competition defines social and economic relations, where citizens are redefined as consumers, democratic choices are exercised by market interactions which reward merit and punishes (what is tautologically defined as) inefficiency. Any intervention into the market (whether through taxation or regulation) is defined as a threat to liberty, public services should be privatized, and inequality is a reward while efforts at creating a more equal society are self-evidently counterproductive. In the end, according to Klein (2007: 444), the core principles of neoliberalism: 'privatization, deregulation and cuts to government services – had laid the foundation for the breakdowns' that would inevitably follow.

By the beginning of the 21st Century, into the now well-established neoliberal 'austerity' society⁴, local governments had become increasingly dependent on the financial markets and their ever more convoluted debt instruments to raise the funds needed to operate and provide services to their constituencies. Localities were in fiscal decline as their ability to generate revenues from local sources fell, whether because of a loss of employers, economic changes due to the shift from manufacturing to services and retail, the proliferation of low-wage or unskilled work, or simply as a result of a declining population. It is no surprise that, across the USA, the poorest cities and rural communities experienced financial

¹ Burns (2011) reflects on how the failure of the PATCO strike and Reagan's actions initiated the long decline of the influence of labour unions in US political and economic life. Coldrick (2013) offers a similar reflection of the impact of Thatcher's breaking the miner's strike on unions, and especially the people of Yorkshire.

² Polanyi argues that there is a self-correcting aspect of capitalism with the double movement, and yet a closer look at global efforts to mediate and off-set the worst aspects of capitalism reveals a woefully inadequate responses (see Fasenfest and Ciancanelli, 2017).

³ Increasingly, neoliberalism in its current manifestation has become the topic of research. See Leshem (2016) for a more traditional account of neoliberalism as the historical outgrowth of religion and market economies, and Becchio and Leghissa (2017) for neoliberalism as a theory of organization and a description of how neoliberalism transformed the political nature of economic activity, especially Chapter 4: Turning the World into a Firm.

⁴ For a general discussion of austerity, its roots and implications, see Blyth, 2013

emergencies and the threat of default and insolvency (substantively similar fiscal crises of lower levels of government took place in the UK and other advanced capitalist economies). Urban and rural poverty intensified as a result of local political units being unable to provide the necessary modalities of social support due to the austerity regime¹. As Mirowski (2013) stresses, neoliberalism survived the 2008 financial shock (even as it is widely understood to be central to its causes), but its initiatives and policies still inform current government practices.

Why Marx, Why Now

Marx's intellectual work reflects, and seeks to promote, radically democratic and anti-capitalist social change. This includes a materialist-realist and dialectical ontology and epistemology and historical-materialist generalizations about all forms of class society, including tools to interpret their deeply held prejudices and material practices against oppressed groups such as women and racialized minorities. In this context, Marx undertakes a political economy of capitalist society, including its economy, state, culture and ecological transformation, including ideas about revolutionary political practice. Marx is fundamentally a dialectical materialist:

My dialectic method is not only different from the Hegelian, but is its direct opposite... [in the sense that] the ideal is nothing else than the material world reflected by the human mind, and translated into forms of thought (*Marx, Afterword to the 2nd German Edition of Capital Vol. 1*).

Marx's materialism is about the production and reproduction of the means of life;

that is, how humans produce/reproduce (a) their bodies which have material needs, and (b) the material conditions of production (e.g. produced spatial organization, environment, technology, etc.) of the means of subsistence through both the interaction of labour with nature, and the social relations of production, property and domestic labour. In this way, societies reproduce themselves.

In his analysis, Marx is guided by four key principles. First, the materiality of human life and human society. Second, the centrality of social relations, that is, the idea that an object or an individual is an ensemble of social relations forming a totality. Third, the systemic and totalizing character of society and, fourth, that social change is driven by internal contradictions. Society as an ensemble of relations, a site where all things are inter-related, though some of the mechanisms are not observable easily or directly; to uncover them Marx makes use of the method of abstraction. He separates what is essential from what is accidental; he looks at phenomena, processes and relations from certain vantage points abstracting from others, and he adjusts the meaning, significance and scope of each concept depending on the level of abstraction of the analysis.

Arguably, Marx's philosophical ideas – especially, his stress on the materiality of life – are highly relevant when the material needs of the majority remain unmet. In this sense, Marx's dialectical-materialist approach allows us to view society in terms of its stark *material* problems (lack of food, shelter or clothing, as well as less immediately visible problems of overwork, debt, low self-esteem, and so on). These symptoms of the contradictions and limitations of capitalism are examined in terms of their (logical) necessity, systemic significance, internal relations

¹ The devastation of neoliberal policies and austerity is clear on society more generally, and on local communities of the poor and disenfranchised more specifically (see Fasenfest 2018, 2020).

to imperialism, and so on. Marx, while writing his *Preface to the Critique of Political Economy* in the mid-19th Century, states that 'one cannot judge' either a time period or a place 'by its consciousness, but, on the contrary, this consciousness must be explained from the contradictions of material life, from the conflict existing between the social forces of production and the relations of production'.

Marx's method is incompatible with superficial generalizations¹, and he emphasizes that categories and hypotheses derived from historical analyses of Western Europe are not to be simply transferred to other social realities:

Thus, events strikingly analogous but taking place in different historic surroundings led to totally different results. By studying each of these forms of evolution separately and then comparing them one can easily find the clue to this phenomenon, but one will never arrive there by the universal passport of a general historico-philosophical theory, the supreme virtue of which consists in being super-historical (Marx, 1977).

This does not mean that one cannot make any scientific generalization based on abstraction about underlying mechanisms that operate widely: for example, if capitalism is to happen and become a dominant relation, separation of direct producers on a large scale is always necessary. However, whether that separation happens in a politically enforced way, through imperial occupation, or through class-differentiation among commodity producers, is a separate matter.

Marx applies his analytical approach to the study of society. Human beings,

as a part of nature, have material needs (food, shelter, clothing, etc.) as well as cultural needs, with the material needs having a degree of priority, in the very broad sense that unless they are satisfied there can be no human life left to produce culture. To satisfy these elementary needs, humans must interact with nature and with another. In doing so, they combine their labour with the means of production that are ultimately derived from nature, in the context of historically specific social relations of production. When the productive forces develop a surplus is produced, and with it, class inequality and class struggle over surplus ensues. In a capitalist class society, whether in the Global South or the North, the means of production are controlled by a small minority, so the great majority have to perform surplus labour. As Marx writes:

Wherever a part of society possesses the monopoly of the means of production, the worker, free or unfree, must add to the labour time necessary for his own maintenance an extra quantity of labour-time in order to produce the means of subsistence for the owner of the means of production, whether this proprietor be ... a slave owner ... or a modern landlord or a capitalist (Marx, 1977: 344).

The state and ideology emerge historically to reinforce and support class inequality. These economic, political, institutional, cultural and ideological processes interact within a whole in which the economy is ultimately – though not immediately – dominant. In common parlance, people must be able to eat, drink, have shelter and clothing and medicine, and so on, before they can pursue politics, science, art, or religion; moreover, the mode of production of material life, the way we produce our

¹ For an overview of Marx's materialist dialectical method, see Saad-Filho (2002, ch.1).

livelihood, conditions our social, political and intellectual life process in general. Once again, here is Marx:

Each particular mode of production and the social relations corresponding to it at each given moment, in short, 'the economic structure of society', is 'the real foundation on which arises the juridical and political superstructure and to which correspond definite forms of social consciousness' ... '[T]he mode of production of material life conditions the general process of social, political, and intellectual life' ... [T]he middle ages could not live on Catholicism, nor the ancient world on politics (Marx, 1977: 175-176).

Throughout the long arch of history, human societies have evolved through various forms of class-based organization (slavery, feudalism, capitalism, etc.). Capitalism as a mode of production is defined by the generalisation of the production of commodities (that is, good and services for sale), for profit by the owners of the means of production, and by means of wage labour employing for the purpose of production of profit. In contrast, in pre-capitalist societies commodities may circulate but mainly to satisfy the direct needs of their producers.

When the direct producers are subjected to what Marx called primitive accumulation, i.e. when they are coercively dispossessed of their means of production (or means of employment and livelihood), they must work for capitalists for a wage. For Marx, the employment relationship under these circumstances results in workers' exploitation through the extraction of surplus value, which benefits capitalists, whose wealth tends to expand cumulatively (see Saad-Filho, forthcoming). As Marx points out in *Capital*, the fact that half a day's labour

is necessary to keep the labourer alive for 24 hours, does not in any way prevent them from working a whole day for the capitalist, thereby producing not only goods and services, but profits too.

For Marx, commodity production under capitalist social relations results in first, concentration and centralization of productive forces in fewer hands (and fewer areas), and second, a more or less constant tendency towards investment in means of production relative to investment in wages, creating a tendency towards the decline of the rate of profit, which he examined together with the counter-tendencies lifting the profit rate. The results are turbulence, volatility and, ultimately, economic crisis; the expansion of a reserve army of unemployed and underemployed workers, resulting in their immiseration in absolute and relative terms (that is, rising inequality between workers and owners of the means of production); proletarianization of independent commodity producers; and concentration and centralization of productive forces. These result in massive adverse impacts on nature and on human bodies (for example, through unsafe working conditions) as well as alienation.

Marx On Poverty

An analysis of poverty informed by Marx is fundamentally about changes in economies and societies, focusing on growth, distribution, the creation of new commodities, the introduction of new technologies, the transformation of needs, and so on. Such an analysis brings to the fore seven ways in which capitalism creates poverty. These include, first, the primitive or original accumulation of capital, concerning the dispossession of non-capitalist classes and their transformation into wage workers. Second, the commodification of production, which

requires waged work for the satisfaction of needs, and creates relative poverty through differential earning capacities and patterns of consumption. Third, the subsumption of petty commodity production, which remains widespread, and exists in complex relations with advanced capitalism. Petty commodity production can absorb market risks and environmental risks, and it offers capital a reservoir of 'informal' labour in different forms.

Fourth, unemployment, which Marx described as the industrial reserve army created by technical change and by market fluctuations; the unemployed help to regulate accumulation, while they also objectively disempower the employed workers, as Kalecki (1943) described clearly. Fifth, the pauperisation of those lacking the capacity or inclination to produce profit, for example, because of age or health conditions; those groups are vulnerable to exploitation in exchange and super exploitation at work. Sixth, system dynamics, including both technological change and economic crises where the most vulnerable suffer through temporary unemployment and the destruction of entire industries. Seventh, because capitalism is indifferent to the social consequences of what it produces. This includes harmful commodities, like weapons or tobacco, and products like rubbish, nuclear waste, pesticide residues, etc.: outcomes that weigh disproportionately upon the poor.

Although capitalism creates unprecedented wealth, Marx stresses that capitalist growth does not necessarily or inevitably eliminate poverty. There is a fatal failure in failing to distinguish between growth and development; the former reflects the increase in the economy, the latter how that increase is manifested in the social relations. For example, mainstream

definitions of poverty tend to focus on one's inability to reach an arbitrary level of income; consequently, they cannot distinguish between poverty caused by low levels of output or productivity from poverty caused by the accumulation of capital. Instead, neoclassical analyses suggest simplistically that 'more surplus value' and 'more growth' will necessarily eliminate poverty.

In contrast, political economy analyses informed by Marx suggest that capital accumulation both creates and eliminates poverty, and it both generates and reduces inequality. In most if not all traditions in the social sciences, the overall impact of growth on poverty and inequality will depend on the structure of the growth process and the mediations of policy. Marx's work focuses on how the accumulation of capital creates different forms of poverty.

This carries three implications: First is that, unquestionably, Marx offers a richer representation of poverty, inequality, and their dynamics than does mainstream economics. Second, poverty and inequality are both structural and tendential under capitalism, and their persistence can be explained by political means. So, poverty and inequality are not just situations that we experience as a society: they are outcomes of policy choices. Third, there is no way to interpret these processes in individualistic terms. Collectivity is essential for the analysis of the creation and reproduction of poverty. This means a class analysis, not as a requirement of ideology, but as an imposition of reality.

Of course, Marx recognises that capitalism systematically raises the productivity of labour, and the working class may capture material benefits from this; however, the nature and extent of these gains will be determined by collective action and not by impersonal

economic laws: once again, individualistic and ahistorical analyses of poverty will not take us far.

This line of argument can be put in more general terms. Marx's theory of poverty is grounded on his theory of value, and the theory of value is not primarily a theory of exchange or even primarily a theory of the creation of wealth and value. It is, instead, a theory of the class relations in capitalist society, showing that capitalism is just one form of exploitative class society, that there are specific class-based paths of transition from non-capitalism to capitalism, that the operation of a capitalist economy can be understood through an analysis of value and class, and it shows why non-Marxist approaches explain the functioning of capitalism in different ways.

Politics for Promoting Human Development

Democratic goals and processes are inherently worthwhile, and they are more attuned to the interests of the vast majority than economic strategies associated with the mainstream and the international financial markets. The implementation of the democratic and redistributive economic strategies suggested in what follows depends less on their internal consistency, that anyway can be demonstrated, than on political limitations. The most important constraint to democratic economic strategies is not resource scarcity, as in mainstream economics, and certainly not theoretical limitations. What limits their implementation is the lack of sufficient political capacity to enforce alternatives based on the joint efforts of governments, political economists, the workers' movement, and civil society.

It is obvious that public policy must play a key role in a democratic

economic strategy, not just because of the imperatives of resource mobilisation, international influence, and the law, but because the state is a fundamental tool for collective action. The state is the only social institution that is at least potentially democratically accountable, and that can influence the pattern of employment, the production and distribution of goods and services, and the distribution of income and assets at the level of society as a whole, to align economic activity with the demands of the majority. The only way to overcome the overlapping weaknesses of the poor is through their political mobilisation.

This should be welcomed, as it is essential in order to counter the strength of capitalist interests, and the drag of all kinds of inequalities upon the condition of the poor. Mass mobilisation can offer the poor avenues for the expression of their needs, and it will give political leverage to governments pursuing greater economic and political democracy. The policy arguments outlined here are not meant to offer a programme of action, but only to point to a direction of travel, and to illustrate the potential implications, in practice, of the analysis of poverty inspired by Marx, in contrast with the intellectual and practical sterility of neoclassical economic thinking, especially in the current conditions of a spreading authoritarian neoliberalism.

It is generally accepted that there can be no left politics without strong mass movements, especially if we expect practical achievements rather than proclamations. Of course, as a society we are in a dire situation partly because of the weakness of the working class. But political debates around the improvement of the situation of the class, the importance of the decommodification of social reproduction, and so on, will

themselves strengthen the left. At a further remove, it is not for academics or conferences to 'write recipes for the cookshops of the future', as Marx once said about himself. At most, we can think logically consistent thoughts, grounded on history, but the implementation of a revolutionary programme, in however many stages may be required – is a practical problem that we academics cannot influence any more than anyone else. The point, as Marx argued, is that there can be no political democracy without economic democracy, and economic equality is essential for political equality: political democracy without economic democracy ends up being a program to protect the rights of property, a situation that points to growing inequality and persistent poverty. In another way, democracy and equality are mutually essential to allow everyone to become an equal member of society, and to realise their potential: ultimately, these goals are incompatible with capitalism.

How to get there is the same practical political problem that the left has been addressing for generations, as it attempts to realise its historical ambition to free people from the dictatorship of moneyed interests, from destitution due to large-scale property, and from inequality engendered by wealth and multiple privileges. The reality is that only a class project can be truly emancipatory. The challenge, under the conditions of a society moulded by a heavily financialised and authoritarian neoliberalism and in crisis because of the spiralling threats of finance, inequality, poverty and environmental crisis, is to draw on the left traditions of struggle against capitalism as a system, and to connect local struggles that make sense to people on the ground, with a general transformative programme pegged around the working class as the only social group possessing both, an immediate interest in resisting

capitalist exploitation but also, at least potentially, the collective power to end it.

Yet, currently working-class action is at its lowest for two generations, and labour has been suffering the heaviest defeats in several decades. But if Marxist analysis is good for anything, it is to tell us that the end of capitalism will come about through social struggles or not at all. At a more immediate level, we can aim to destabilise neoliberalism, which will require attacking its material basis through a set of democratic economic policy initiatives supporting a shift to more equal distributions of income, wealth and power, and higher levels of material welfare for the poor, in order to promote human development and alleviate poverty both locally and globally. These are fundamental conditions for democracy – not a conventional neoliberal democracy, but a radical democracy as it was imagined by Marx, and that must inevitably be incompatible with capitalism. This strategy must be supported by a politically re-articulated working class as one of the main levers for its own economic re-composition.

The practical difficulty is that this virtuous circle cannot be just wished into being. Its elements cannot be addressed purely academically, or through the organisation of another political party, or through alliances between the already existing forces of the left. The construction of a new economic, social and political model destabilising capitalism will require mass mobilisations strong enough not just to demand change from governments, or even changes of government, but to transform the state, through organised mass action, and also taking over the state from within, through the appropriation, neutralisation and re-invention of progressive institutions.

Without a revolutionary perspective and theory, the majority of people will continue to be oppressed as is witnessed

by the countless examples of people who appeared to win their struggle yet failed to emancipate themselves from the new enemies. We have to learn from their tragedies. A socialist progressive solution cannot survive indefinitely within a larger capitalist framework. Socialism surrounded by capitalism can become authoritarian

over people in order to defend its political and economic regime from imperialism. So how should we construct an alternative true socialism? This is the task which all Marxists must embrace for people's emancipation from the imperialism and potentially distorted forms of socialism.

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